

CHEMICAL REACTIVITY AND LIGHT ABSORPTION.

PART IV.

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Total absorption of light by a mixture of the reacting substances has been observed to be greater than the absorption of each substance taken separately in reactions studied in the present paper. The increase in light absorption in each case varies with the concentration of the reducing agent. The dark reaction velocity also decreases with the decrease of concentration of the reducing agent. The chemical reactivity and the increase in the light absorption by a mixture are almost equally affected by a change in concentration of the reducing agent. The increased light absorption appears to be due to the activation of molecules in the presence of the molecules of the sensitising agents. The activation of the molecules is associated with loosening of the binding forces and the consequent increased light absorption.

In previous publications (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 33, 311, 629; *Indian J. Phys.*, 1936, 10, 43) it has been shown that the introduction of a reactive chemical substance in a light absorbing substance increases its power of absorbing light. The increased absorption appears to be due to the activation of the molecules of the absorbing substance. It has also been shown that in the reaction between sodium formate and iodine an increase in the concentration of one of the reacting components leads to an increase in light absorption by a mixture of sodium formate and iodine. From our experimental observations it appears that the heat of reaction and increased light absorption go hand in hand.

In this paper the influence of concentration of one of the reacting components on the chemical reactivity and light absorption in the case of several reactions has been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

For photographing the absorption spectra, two spectrographs (Adam Hilger, Quartz Spectrograph, Types E₃ and E₁) were used. In these experiments a copper arc worked with 220 volts and 4.5 amperes was utilised as a source of light. The reaction vessel was of quartz with internal dimensions 13 cm. × 3 cm. × 5 cm. Results have been recorded below.

Oxalic Acid and Chlorine.—Both the reacting substances being photo-sensitive, the reaction is very fast in absence of hydrochloric acid, and its velocity is difficult to measure. Hence hydrochloric acid was added to retard the reaction. The photographs and the following results show that

the greater the concentration of oxalic acid and hence the greater the velocity, the greater is the absorption of light by the mixture (Table I).

TABLE I.

Oxalic acid.	Increase in light absorption by the mixture.	k_1 (unimol. vel. coeff. in region $\lambda = 3125\text{\AA}$.)
N/16	324 $\text{\AA}$	0.1209
N/20	254 $\text{\AA}$	0.067

TABLE II.

Ferrous sulphate.	Increase in light absorption by the mixture.
4%	162 $\text{\AA}$
%	92 $\text{\AA}$

Ferrous Sulphate and Iodine.—In this reaction also an aqueous solution of iodine was used. Both the components are light sensitive (Table II).

Sodium Tartrate and Iodine.—Increased light absorption by the mixture is observed with increase in the concentration of the tartrate solution.

Sodium Formate and Iodine.—Dhar and Bhargava (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, **39**, 1231) investigated the light absorption by mixture of sodium formate and iodine dissolved in potassium iodide. In this paper, the results obtained by using aqueous solutions of iodine are recorded (Table III).

TABLE III.

Sodium formate.	Increased light absorption by the mixture	k_1 (unimol. vel. coeff. in the dark).
N/2	162 $\text{\AA}$	0.246
N/4	92 $\text{\AA}$	0.124

TABLE IV.

Hydroxylamine hydrochloride.	Total absorption from wavelength.
N/2	3028 $\text{\AA}$
N/4	2905 $\text{\AA}$
N/20	2823 $\text{\AA}$

Hydroxylamine Hydrochloride and Iodine.—In this reaction as well as in the reaction with hydrazine sulphate hydrochloric acid has to be added, as the reaction was too fast to be measured in absence of the acid (Tables IV and V).

TABLE V.

Hydrazine sulphate and iodine.
(HCl added.)

Hydrazine sulphate.	Increased light absorption by the mixture.
N/50	208 $\text{\AA}$
N/100	185 $\text{\AA}$
N/500	162 $\text{\AA}$

TABLE VI.

Ferrous ammonium sulphate and silver nitrate.

Ferrous ammonium sulphate.	Increase in light absorption by the mixture.
0.4%	46 $\text{\AA}$
0.2%	25 $\text{\AA}$

Acetone and Iodine.—In this reaction also, the greater the concentration of acetone, the greater is the light absorption by the mixture.

It was shown by Dawson and others (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **95**, 1860; 1913, **103**, 2135) that the reaction between acetone and iodine is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The effect of the catalyst is only to increase the velocity

of enolisation of acetone, which takes place according to the following scheme :—

This increase in velocity is directly proportional to the concentration of hydrogen ions. We have photographed the absorption spectra of the mixture of acetone and iodine, using a wide range of concentration of hydrochloric acid, *viz.*, from 12.0 N to 0.17 N. The results are recorded on Plate I. The spectra shows a regular decrease in absorption as the concentration of hydrochloric acid decreases.

These results lend strong evidence in support of the view that the increase in light absorption is the direct result of the increased chemical reactivity of the molecules.

Potassium Permanganate and Hydrochloric Acid.—The photograph brings out that in this reaction, the greater the concentration of hydrochloric acid the greater is the increase in light absorption by the mixture.

From the photographs it is also evident that complete absorption by the reacting mixture begins from a longer wave-length than that by the reacting components and that the increase in the concentration of the reducing agent leads to more light absorption by the mixture.

Our results further show that with the decrease in concentration of the reducing agent, the velocity of the reactions concerned and the chemical reactivity of the mixture diminishes as also the light absorption. The photographs also reveal that with a very dilute solution of the reducing agent, the mixture does not show any appreciably enhanced absorption and at these concentrations the velocity of the chemical reactions is also almost negligible.

These investigations on the influence of concentration on chemical reactivity and light absorption have further supported the observations of Dhar and Bhattacharya (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 33) that several reactions show marked acceleration by infra-red radiations of wave-lengths 7304 Å and 8500 Å because the presence of the reducing agent markedly sensitises the decomposition of the other molecules.

These observations showing that the chemical reactivity between the substances is accompanied by increased light absorption, and this phenomenon of sensitised decomposition bring to a close the long controversy regarding the minimum frequency of radiations capable of initiating the chlorine-hydrogen reaction, because in presence of hydrogen the Cl-Cl

link is considerably weakened and hence radiation of wave-lengths longer than $5000 \text{ \AA}$, which are capable of atomising a chlorine molecule, can initiate the chemical change.

From our results with mixtures of hydrogen and chlorine, hydrogen and bromine vapour, methyl alcohol vapour and bromine vapour, ethyl alcohol vapour and bromine vapour etc., it is clear that the light absorption by a mixture of the reacting substances occurs over a wider region of the spectrum than in the case of absorptions by the ingredients considered separately. It is interesting to note, that there is no variation in the position of the absorption limit when the gases or vapours are passed through concentrated sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide. In other words, desiccation considerably decreases the chemical reactivity and prevents the combination of hydrogen and chlorine or hydrogen and bromine in the visible region. Hydrogen sensitises the dissociation of chlorine and bromine molecules and makes them reactive in radiations of longer wave-lengths only in the presence of moisture. These observations support the important work of Baker who showed that intensive drying greatly reduces the reaction velocity of substances. Baker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 1402) and Tamm (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1923, 105, 356) showed that hydrogen and chlorine, dried over phosphorus pentoxide did not combine at all in visible light. Coehn and Jung (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 110, 705) found that there was no combination in the system where the pressure of water vapour was estimated to be 10 mm. of Hg., no reaction occurred even after 20 days' exposure to sunlight, but that the reaction took place rapidly when the pressure was 10^{-5} mm. Bodenstein and Dux had found that the variation of water vapour between 10 mm. and 10^{-3} mm. had no effect on reactions between hydrogen and chlorine and concluded that the non-reactivity of gases dried over phosphorus pentoxide might be due to some inhibition.

It can now be stated with a certain amount of definiteness that the appearance of a continuous absorption (non-quantised absorption) spectrum of a gas is always a case of photochemical dissociation taking place in the gas. Moreover, convergence limits in continuous absorption have up till now been observed only for those molecules in which the binding forces are appreciably weakened by light absorption.

It appears, therefore, that increase in light absorption by a molecule is associated with it increased reactivity and loosening of the binding forces. Conversely when a molecule becomes more reactive, it is likely to absorb light more markedly.

Victor Henri has reported that with an increase of temperature the limit of dissociation is shifted towards the higher wave-length side and that

the radiation corresponding to the region of predissociation causes photochemical reaction or chemical sensitisation of the molecules.

From the researches of Henri and others, it is clear that on increasing the temperature, the absorption limit is shifted and the molecules dissociate on illumination by radiations of longer wave-lengths. Thus with acetaldehyde, the absorption spectrum at the laboratory temperature consists of a large number of sharp bands with definite structure between λ_{3484} to λ_{3050} . Near λ_{3050} the bands become blurred rapidly due to predissociation of the molecule and about 60 diffuse bands reaching up to λ_{2823} have been measured. Also there is superimposed on these diffuse bands, a broad continuous band starting at about λ_{3080} with a maximum at λ_{2850} and which subsequently falls off in intensity more and more on the ultraviolet side. If acetaldehyde vapour is heated to 200° , feeble diffuse bands appear between λ_{3500} and λ_{3200} with a strong continuous absorption reaching far into the ultraviolet. When acetaldehyde vapour is illuminated at the laboratory temperature, decomposition takes place into CO and CH_4 , only when the wave length is λ_{3002} or shorter ; whilst at 200° , vapour can be photolysed by radiations of wave-length exceeding λ_{3100} .

It appears, therefore, from these researches on photochemical decomposition and predissociation that the increase in the chemical reactivity of a substance by increase of temperature is associated with a shift in the position of the absorption bands specially in the ultraviolet region. Moreover, increased temperature of the molecule sensitises them towards their decomposition by longer wave-lengths. Hence the weakening of the binding forces of molecules and their consequent instability are associated with shift of absorption bands and of the limit of continuous absorption by the molecules.

Just as an increase of temperature or light absorption weakens the binding forces of a molecule, the introduction of a chemical substance into an absorbing system may also loosen the binding forces of a molecule. For example, the presence of a reducing agent accelerates the decomposition of an oxidising molecule. Thus in presence of reducing agents like hydrogen, carbon monoxide, ferrous salts, nitrites, hydroxylamine, alcohols, acetone, organic acids and their salts, etc., the halogen molecules become reactive even in the dark as well as when exposed to radiations of wave-lengths longer than those necessary for their sensitised or photochemical dissociation, because the binding forces of the halogen molecules are considerably weakened due to the presence of the reducing agents.

It has been shown previously with numerous reactions taking place in solutions that the light absorption by a mixture of the reacting substances

is always greater than the absorption of the ingredients considered separately. The increase in absorption appears to be due to the activation of the molecules by the presence of the molecules of the other substances. The activation of the molecules is associated with the weakening of the binding forces and consequent increased light absorption.

The observations of Weigert and Kellermann (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1923, **107**, 1) on increased light absorption by a mixture of chlorine and hydrogen and the increased light absorption observed by J. C. Ghosh and collaborators (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **5**, 353 ; 1928, **5**, 191, 569), with mixtures of organic substances and solutions of ferric and mercuric chlorides, and uranyl nitrate, can be interpreted on the viewpoint that the chemical reactivity of these various systems is associated with the weakening of the binding forces and increased light absorption. Fajans and Karagunis (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, **B5**, 385) have shown that the light absorption by silver iodide containing adsorbed silver is appreciably greater than that of silver iodide containing adsorbed iodine or that of silver iodide alone. Moreover, it is well known that the silver halides containing adsorbed silver are more photosensitive and hence more liable to be decomposed in light than the silver halides containing an excess of the halogen. Similar results have been obtained with other silver halides. The presence of silver sensitises the photodecomposition of silver halides and weakens the binding forces between silver and the halogen atoms and causes increased light absorption. From the above facts it can be concluded that the contact of one reacting substance with another weakens the binding forces of the molecules of reacting substances just as increase of temperature or light absorption loosens the binding forces. The close proximity or contact of another molecular species capable of chemically reacting with the first one, plays practically the same rôle as that of the physical agencies, *viz.* increase of temperature or light absorption.

From the numerous cases cited in this paper it seems clear to us that if there is possibility of the occurrence of a chemical change by mixing two or more substances, variation in the position of the absorption limit is likely to be observed in these cases. We are of opinion that the shift in the position of the absorption limit in the case of a mixture in comparison with those of the ingredients is likely to be a measure of the reactivity of a given mixture of two or more substances.

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PLATE I.

Oxalic acid and chlorine.

Exposure = 5 secs.

3153
3274
2618

2294

1. Cu arc.
2. $N/150$ -chlorine.
3. ($12 N\text{-HCl} + N/5$ -oxalic acid)+water.
4. ($12 N\text{-HCl} + N/5$ -oxalic acid)+ $N/75$ -chlorine.

PLATE II.

Influence of the variation of conc. of HCl on the light absorption of acetone and iodine reaction.

Exposure = 10 sec.

3153
3274
3618
2394

1. Cu arc.
2. $N/680$ -Iodine.
3. ($r\%$ acetone + $12N\text{-HCl}$) + H_2O .
4. (" + $12N$ - ") + $N/340$ -I
5. (" + $6N$ - ") + H_2O .
6. (" + " ") + $N/340$ -I
7. (" + $3N$ - ") + H_2O .
8. (" + " ") + $N/340$ -I
9. (" + $17N$ - ") + H_2O .
10. (" + " ") + $N/340$ -I
11. (" + $0.85N$ - ") + H_2O .
12. (" + " ") + $N/340$ -I
13. (" + $0.17N$ - ") + H_2O .
14. (" + " ") + $N/340$ -I

PLATE III.
Sodium tartrate and iodine.
Exposure = 5 sec.

5153

3274

2618

2294

1. Cu arc.
2. $N/680\text{-I}_2$.
3. $N/4\text{-tartrate}$.
4. $N/2\text{-tartrate} + N/340\text{-I}_3$.
5. $N/200\text{-tartrate}$.
6. $N/100\text{-tartrate} + N/340\text{-I}_2$.

PLATE IV.
Sodium formate and iodine.
Exposure = 3 sec.

5153

3274

2618

2294

1. Cu arc.
2. $N/680\text{-I}_2$.
3. $N/4\text{-formate}$.
4. $N/2\text{-formate} + N/340\text{-I}_2$.
5. $N/8\text{-formate}$.
6. $N/4\text{-formate} + N/340\text{-I}_2$.
7. $N/40\text{-formate}$.
8. $N/20\text{-formate} + N/340\text{-I}_2$.

PLATE V.

Hydroxylamine hydrochloride and iodine.

Exposure = 3 sec.

5153

3274

2618

2294

1. Cu arc.
2. $N/680-I_2$.
3. $N/4$ -Hydroxylamine HCl.
4. $N/2-$,, + $N/340-I_2$.
5. $N/8-$,,
6. $N/4-$,, + $N/340-I_2$.
7. $N/40-$,,
8. $N/20-$,, + $N/340-I_2$.

PLATE VI.

Hydrazine sulphate + iodine.

Exposure = 3 sec.

5135

3274

2618

2204

1. Cu arc.
2. $N/680-I_2$.
3. $N/100$ -Hydrazine sulphate.
4. $N/50-$,, + $N/340-I_2$.
5. $N/200-$,,
6. $N/100$,, + ,,
7. $N/1000-$,,
8. $N/500-$,, + ,,

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PLATE VII.

HCl + KMnO_4 .

Exposure = 15 sec.

5153

3774

2168

2594

1. Cu arc.

2. $N/200\text{-KMnO}_4$.

3. $1/25\text{-N-HCl}$

4. $2/5\text{N-HCl} + N/100\text{-KMnO}_4$.

5. $N/2\text{-HCl}$.

6. $\text{N-HCl} + N/100\text{-KMnO}_4$.